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ROLE OF TOUCH FOR ENRICHING REMOTE INTERPERSONAL INTERACTION OVER DIGITAL PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Remote Interpersonal Interaction (RII) is an emerging research theme aims to support / enrich interpersonal interaction when the people are physically separated from each other. This has been an important design topic as the network and mobile communication technologies develop. In this paper, we aim to understand and find ways to apply “Touch” for RII over digital products. We present critical review of existing literature and suggestions of future directions on the application of touch in RII. First, we investigated features of current channels that are mostly used in RII over mobile phones and computers. Second, we showed the importance of touch interaction in the aspect of effective/emotional human interaction and the social meanings of interpersonal touch. Third, we reviewed several prototypes and empirical studies that had applied touch to enrich RII. And we identify limitations of previous cases and suggest several ways to apply touch in designing digital products with RII features. This paper help designers understand and better apply touch in product design for enriching RIIs.

Keywords: Remote interpersonal interaction, touch, emotional communication

INTRODUCTION

Most of our daily social interactions are mediated by textual and audio channels, such as written mail, instant text messaging, or audio communication through telephone. Those influences a person’s interactions when physically and temporally separated. We often use those media to share ideas, music, photos, feelings and emotions with family members, friends, and colleagues. Such devices as

mobile phones help us feel connected with others. Their importance as an emotional communication medium is growing as our life style is being individualized (Norman, 2004). Emotional communication using traditional communication devices depends on text, video or phonetic features such as amplitude variation, pitch inflections, tempo, duration, filtration, tonality and rhythm. For effective emotional communication in our daily lives, however, verbal and non-verbal behaviors such as facial expressions, touching behaviors and gestures should be in harmony (Knapp & Hall, 1978). Video phones are being developed in this respect, but they introduce other problems of privacy and an unnatural communication posture. In order to support more emotional and rich daily communication, it is important to consider touch to exchange contextual and nonverbal cues (Wang & Quek, 2010). Touch is a significant communication channel for affection. Even a short touch can elicit strong emotional experience (Haans & IJsselsteijn, 2006). However the application of touch in our daily communication is restricted, especially when human-to-human interactions are being mediated by communication devices such as mobile phones. The addition of a touch channel to communication devices can be a unique and immediate channel for affective interaction when considerations of the context are required. Since touch is indispensably related to intimacy, touch allows for personal and intimate interactions in ways that words, sounds or images presumably cannot (Haans & IJsselsteijn, 2006). The goal of this paper is to understand and find ways to apply touch for RII over digital products. In this paper, we present critical review of existing literature and suggestions of future directions on the

application of touch in RII. First, we investigated features of current channels that are mostly used in RII over mobile phones and computers. Second, we showed the importance of touch interaction in the aspect of effective/emotional human interaction and the social meanings of interpersonal touch. Third, we reviewed several prototypes and empirical studies that had applied touch to enrich RII. And we identified limitations of previous cases and suggested several ways to apply touch in designing communicative digital products.

THEORICAL BASIS OF REMOTE INTERPERSONAL INTERACTIONS (RII)

UNDERSTANDING RII

The term “Remote Interpersonal Interaction” had been used from many researchers in the HCI field whose researches aim to support / enrich interpersonal interaction when the users are physically separated from each other. Originally, the term came from the area of computer-mediated communication (CMC) which covers a whole process of human communication via computers, involving people, situated in particular contexts and engaging in processes to shape media for a variety of purposes (Walther, 1997). Representative forms of the media used in remote interpersonal interaction can be voice, text and video. Those have been the most commonly used channel to date. E-mail, on-line chat and bulletin boards have been widely used in the internet era.

Research in this field focuses largely on the social effects of different computer-supported communication technologies and many recent studies involve Internet-based social networking supported by social software. There have also been research works on the emotional value of digital products that support for remote interpersonal interaction in our everyday lives (e.g. mobile phones, PDAs, tablet computers and keyboards). Short et al (1976) found social presence theory that different communication media enable different levels of experience of the social presence of individuals who are engaged in the communication. The level of experience of the social presence of the other user is related to the quality of the medium. The “medium” in the theory can be understood as digital products that mediate the

communication for the users who are physically separated. In this situation, the richness of interpersonal communication through the digital products is highly affected by the design of the product itself. The designer’s roles are becoming more important to design a product to support users to have higher social presence, friendliness and emotional values when they communicate with the other in remote. Better user experience of digital products will be achieved from understanding how the designers understand people’s face-to-face interaction that naturally happens in our everyday lives.

FEATURES OF CHANNELS FOR RII

A variety of channels exists for remote interpersonal interactions. We examined the advantages and limitations of existing channels focusing on emotional values that might affect the quality of interaction and product experience.

Voice channel

Remote interpersonal interaction is highly dependent on voice channel because of its abilities of conveying information, intend, emotion and personality. Voice channel was naturally used as most frequent communication channel over the centuries since Bell (1877) had founded Telephone Company. Voice channel can convey emotions through vocal cues that accompany spoken words. For decades, researchers studied that emotions are delivered through the voice. In general, anger, joy, and sadness are easier to recognize than fear and disgust in the voice; shame and love were found to be most difficult to recognize (Banse & Scherer, 1996; Pittam and Scherer, 1993). According to the media richness theory (Daft & Lengel, 1986), the transmission of rich information in remote interpersonal communication requires instantaneous feedback and a higher level of interactivity. In this perspective, video and voice channels are richer than text channel. Scherer (1972) conducted an empirical study on which kind of vocal features affect the emotion expressions. He gave participants 9 kinds of voice features (Amplitude, pitch variation & contour & level, tempo, filtration, tonality and rhythm) in an artificial sound and let them to rate with 12 different emotions (interest, sadness, fear, happiness, disgust, anger, surprise,

elation, and boredom). Their result showed that pitch and tempo were highly influential for feeling emotions through voice channel. However, verbal and nonverbal systems operate together as a part of the larger communication process. Vocal behavior occupies few percentages while gesture, posture, touching behavior, facial expression and eye behavior are dominant factor for recognizing emotions.

Text channel

Text channel is the most frequently used synchronous/asynchronous channel for remote interpersonal interaction that it is efficient for keeping privacy and fast information transmission. On the other hand, media richness of text channel is lower than other channels like voice and video because it lacks nonverbal cues that are the most important part of our communication. As our lives are getting more individualized, the privacy issues in our communications are getting more important and in this situation voice and video channels may cause privacy problems. Recently, Hancock et al. (2007) explored expressing emotion in text-based communication. They categorized 8 strategy types from the 40 participants that they often use to express emotion in text-based communication. Those were punctuation, more typing, emoticons, explicit emotion statements, partner encouragement, quick response, self disclosure and agreement. The result indicated that when a partner agrees, using punctuation and quick response help the user feel more positive emotion. However, recognizing emotions through text is complex and there are still many cues that users should give an effort to interpret the other's emotion through the sentence itself. In addition, the emotional cues from the text are not generally accepted as common nonverbal behaviors such as touch, which allow users to freely interpret them as their own language.

Video channel

Emotional communication through video channel is effective, because it can convey various non-verbal behaviors such as user's gestures, postures, facial expressions and eye contacts that occupies large portion of emotional communication between people. In video communication, the non-verbal cues aid

verbal spoken words or can work alone such as speech-independent gestures (e.g. "OK" gesture that shaping the two fingers as a circle). Video communication is first developed by Schubert(1936), and it is realized through various devices that could provide video and voice channel together. In South Korea, 2007, commercial video communication service started as another way of communication in our mobile phones. However, video communication introduced other problems of privacy and interaction. Unlike a traditional voice phone call that is made by placing the device on the cheek, a video phone call is made by facing the device. A user's background is exposed to the other party; the background audio can be transmitted to others in the environment unless they wear isolating devices such as earphones; holding the device to capture one's own face could be physically demanding; and some situations necessitate moving the device from optimal positions for video and audio transmission in turn.

Cases using multiple channels for RII

Over the years, researchers have tried to combine the channels to support more emotional remote interpersonal communication. Sundström et al. (2005) conveyed emotional messages by mapping shaking gestures with a mobile phone and the background color of a text message. Chang et al. (2001) developed a prototype that enables emotional communication through the interaction with picture frames - when one user touches his or her picture frame, the other's picture frame lights up). In addition, there were studies to express the presence or movement of dancers in a stage with light boxes (Seitinger et al., 2010) on the floor that the boxes can recognize the vibration and sound of dancer's movement to give audio-visual event in a concert. Quintanilha (2008) used color and posture of buddies (a portable size product that represents color according to the context of a friend) to allow for communication among remotely located friends and to display an awareness of group presence and others' availability through an ambient wall display.

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

From the review, we identified the advantages and limitations of channels that currently support remote

interpersonal interaction in our daily mediated communication over digital products. Non-verbal cues are significant for supporting emotional remote communication. Users are trying to create emotional cues through the expression of verbal cues. Typical example is the text channel that punctuation, agreement or quick response affects the positive/negative emotion in the communication. Also in voice channel, tempo and pitch level affects the emotions. However, those phenomena could sometimes lead to conveying different meanings to the other because symbolic meanings of non-verbal cues from the verbal cues are not equal to all.

Small addition can be effective?

Several researches from the previous section showed that researchers are trying to add minimal features of another channel, for example, using color instead of whole synchronous video images; only a small support from the other channel can enrich verbal / text communication.

Design challenges exist

On the other hand, we face into technological problems when digital products mediate the remote interpersonal interaction, and these might always conflict with price, portability and design issues of products.

Benefits exist if the familiarity of existing communication media is effectively supported in the new interface

Also we should not ignore familiarity and naturalness of channels and interaction behavior. For example, voice call on the cheek using mobile phone is natural however facing to the mobile phone for video call takes time to adapt. These issues might affect the experience of product use.

Designer's role are becoming important to design a product how to enrich emotional interaction by understanding features of the whole channels that are provided in our face-to-face interaction and find ways to deliver non-verbal cues in remote interactions. Some works showed the potentials of combining channels to support emotional communication. Further empirical studies are required to show how those can enrich

communication in remote situation. Among many sensual channels, application of touch has not been fully explored to support remote interpersonal interactions. Although touch by another person can elicit strong affective experiences in everyday situations, it is not commonly used in our daily remote communication.

UNDERSTANDING TOUCH INTERACTION

IMPORTANCE OF TOUCH EXPERIENCE: EFFECTIVE AND EMOTIONAL WAY OF INTERACTION

Interpersonal interaction through touch is probably the most basic form of interaction. Child's first tactual experience is vibrations of the mother's heartbeat and child responds to the feelings in their fetal life. Also child's first tactual experiences with objects mostly involve being touched (Sonneveld, 2008) (e.g. mother cleans the baby with the towels). Field (1998) mentioned that tactual experience of newborns affects their growth. Infants gain knowledge of the world around them through tactual explorations with their mouth and hands (Knapp & Hall, 1978). These facts indicate that early tactual experiences are very crucial to the mental development of children.

When the child grows up, they learn how to use the touching behavior/how to act when they perceive the touching behavior in a certain context. Then as the environment/context changes, they use touch when they think it can be more effective and emotional than saying words. For example, a short patting on the other's shoulder elicits stronger emotional comfort than saying a words like "Cheer up!".

Depends on the environment and context of people, touch can replace words, on the other hand words can replace touch. When the mother says to her child, "It's all right, dear- Mommy's here", words replace touch and conveys intimate closeness / make the child feel relaxedness even if they are in a remote situation.

MEANING OF TOUCH CHANNEL FOR COMMUNICATION

Interpersonal touch communication can be divided into two parts: 1) Active touch: touching other person and 2) Passive touch: being touched by other person (Heller, 1984). The body parts of active touch

and passive touch can be same but also different when we handshake or pinch someone on the cheek. In the active mode we can produce a perception of touch by deciding the method and the purpose of touch. Jones & Yabrough (1985) categorized purposes of touch into seven categories: positive affect touches (to support, appreciate, feel closeness and express sexual interest love), playful touches (for playful affection and playful aggression), control touches (to persuade/force others to do something), ritualistic touches (for greeting and closing an encounter), hybrid touches (to express affection at the initiation / close of an encounter), task-related touch (to do tasks) and accidental touches (unintentional and meaningless). However, negative affect touches are not reported Jones and Yabrough' study. On the other hand in the passive touch mode, we perceive and interpret the meaning of touch by other person.

Pisano et al (1986) categorized the meanings of touch perception from six categories: friendliness, playfulness, warmth/love, sexual desire, comfort/reassurance and dominance/control.

These social meanings of interpersonal touch explain that touch is a significant channel for emotional and effective communication in our everyday lives. In addition, these meanings should be understood before we design remote interpersonal touch communication over digital products.

DISCUSSION: THE TOUCH INTERACTION FROM FACE-TO-FACE TO REMOTE

The meanings of touch depend on environmental, personal and contextual variables. When a person was being touched by the other, it can be interpreted differently by whom, when and where the touching behavior was performed (Knapp & Hall, 1978).

In face-to-face (FtF) interaction, we naturally get personal and environmental information before we start the interaction. And the types of touch can be easily performed / be touched by all kinds of our body parts. In this situation, we could accurately convey our meanings of touch. On the other hand, when two/more people are physically separated and they should communicate with the other by the

mobile phones/computers, environmental information is not shared and touched body parts are limited to where the user is holding or placing their body parts on the digital products. Thus, when the digital products are mediated in remote communication, limitations might occur. First, touching body part and touched body part is already decided as how we use the mediated digital product. In other words, body parts which can perform active touch are limited to the parts of hand that use the mediated digital products (e.g. mobile phones). Body parts that perceive touch are also limited to palms, fingers, cheeks and thighs that hold/put the mediated digital products. Interpersonal communication requires that at least part of the message should have a common or share symbolic meaning. This implies that the intentionality of the message should be commonly agreed upon well (Manusov & Rodriguez, 1989). As we mentioned earlier, non-consistency on the body parts of active/passive touch in product mediated interpersonal communication can make the people feel confuse the commonly agreed symbolic meanings of touch. When the body parts problems are solved, technical limitations might occur with product usability issues. However, first of all, the social and symbolic meanings of touching/touched body part should be investigated thoroughly, and the effectiveness of touch experience must be proved over long-term empirical studies and the guidelines should be well set up before we design/use the product.

REMOTE INTERPERSONAL TOUCH OVER DIGITAL PRODUCTS: CASES AND LIMITATIONS

REMOTE INTERPERSONAL TOUCH OVER DIGITAL PRODUCTS

Haans & Ijsselsteijn (2006) proposed a framework of mediated social touch that can be used to develop techniques of non-verbal and emotional communication between remote persons by using tactile input-output devices. Bailenson et al (2007) refined this concept as a Virtual Interpersonal Touch (VIT) that people touching one another via force-feedback haptic devices. These studies mentioned several advantages and disadvantages of applying

touch in remote interpersonal interactions as followings.

Advantages

First, touch can enhance or enrich mediated communication. It increases the amount of information that can be transferred. Also touch can compensate for the loss of non-verbal cues. In addition, touch increases trust. Second, touch enhances personal and intimate interactions that words or images presumably cannot. And touch is suitable to substitute the other sense in situations where other types of channels are impossible to use, where there are privacy demands and where there is danger of cognitive overload.

Disadvantages

On the other hand, touch has some disadvantages. First, touch interaction requires close distance and physical coupling (restriction of movement). Second, touch is not used as often as facial expressions and voice intonation changes. Third, touch is appropriate for one to one communication only, not one-to-many as the other cues are.

REMOTE TOUCH FOR EMOTIONAL INTERACTION

Several studies have implemented remote interpersonal touch by developing special input/output devices. Brave et al (1998) made a device having three rollers to allow users to convey their presence to each other by moving the device and receiving the movement in real time. Hashimoto & Kajimoto (2008) suggested a method to deliver emotional gestures (e.g., tapping, tickling, pushing and caressing) by sensing using a proximity sensor and by rendering using a woofer. Tsetserukou et al. (2010) devised a wearable device to be worn on users' chest to make them feel hugging and hitting of their digital avatars in Second Life with vibration and heat. For more natural and comfortable interaction, some researchers used objects that can be commonly discovered in daily life as tactile mediators. DiSalvo et al. (2003) presented a prototype to communicate each other's emotions and presence using cushions - when a user strokes, squeezes, hugs, and/or pats it; corresponding light/sound/vibration is delivered to the other's cushion. Similarly, cups (Chung et al., 2006) and chairs (Karam et al., 2010) have been used.

The studies above shows interesting insights on how touch can assist social interaction and suggest the potential of using tactile mediators in emotional communication remotely; however, how real time mapping between expression and perception of touches using the suggested devices is done and how effective they are for conveying touches have not been adequately discussed. In addition, most studies have proposed alternative devices for sharing touches which might require unnatural ways of interaction and demand that users carry specific devices for sharing touch.

REMOTE TOUCH FOR INFORMATION REPRESENTATION

Touch can convey not only emotional content but also practical information. Touch is especially useful to users who are blocked from visual information such as the visually impaired, or in those in restricting situations who cannot give visual information (Ghiani et al., 2008; McDaniel et al., 2009). Brown & Kaaresoja (2006) performed a study about notifications for incoming voice calls, text/multimedia messages by rendering different tactile patterns on a mobile phone. Yatani & Troung (2009) presented eleven kinds of tactile patterns in order to provide lively feelings of information in touch phone usage, and proved that the tactile patterns could be distinguished with more than 70% accuracy. Recently, Huang et al (2010) reported a study using a glove with vibrotactile actuators to help in learning the piano. However, if the mapping of tactile stimuli and the corresponding information is not intuitive, users could become confused during a call.

REMOTE AUDIO-TACTILE SYSTEMS FOR RII

Several studies have investigated to support emotional audio-tactile communication for remote persons. Chang et al. (2002) developed a pair of pads that can deliver the intensity of each finger's pressure with vibrotactile feedback during a voice call. They conducted audio-tactile communication experiments asking each participant to put one hand on the pad placed on the table while wearing headsets. Their results showed that tactile stimulation helps in emphasis, turn-taking and

mimicking during calls. In addition, they suggested a concept of a phone call using an all-in-one mobile phone with the tactile input-output pad on it. Additional implementations and experiments have not been reported using this concept. Wang & Quek (2010) found that if the tactile channel is added to voice communication then it amplifies positive emotions and reduces negative emotions by using an armband-type inflatable wearable tactile device. Interestingly, they mentioned that people in close relationships have strong needs for emotional interaction through mediated touch. However, their idea involves a practical problem - the user should wear additional equipment other than a mobile phone. Not being used in real time communication, Brown and Williams developed a mobile messaging system called Shake2Talk (Brown & Williamson, 2007) that sends flicking, twisting, tapping and stroking gestures along with voice. They conducted an experiment with actual romantic couples and they discovered that Shake2Talk could deliver positive emotions like playful messages or practical information like call-for-action messages (Brown et al., 2009). However their expression level is very limited and a separate gesture recording process is required, which can act as an obstacle in the uninterrupted, continuous audio-tactile communication.

TECHNOLOGIES FOR REMOTE INTERPERSONAL TOUCH

New forms of actuators have been developed to give actual tactile feelings like human touch. Harrison et al (2009) and Wang et al (2010) used thin shape memory alloys (SMA). Because their movement is delicate, slow, and quiet, actuators using SMA do not cause discomfort to users wrapped with fabrics like woven elastic, spandex, cotton, and latex, thus they are good for developing wearable devices. Poupyrev et al. (2002) developed thin paper-like tactile actuators that can output subtle and ambient tactile feelings without giving displeasure to the users. Li et al. (2008) developed a prototype to provide tapping and rubbing feelings using a voice coil motor and a small hammer. Bau et al. (2009) developed a thin tactile output device to provide poking feelings by applying the principles of electromagnetic stimulation. The most widely used tactile actuator by HCI researchers are coin-type vibrotactile

actuators (Chang et al., 2002; Chung et al., 2006; Yatani & Truong, 2009; Tsetserukou et al., 2010), because they are cheap and small enough to be used in large arrays on existing equipment or in sponge, cotton, and cloth to make various forms of tactile output devices.

DISCUSSION

The studies above showed interesting insights and suggested a certain level of possibility of using tactile mediators in emotional communication in remote. In case of using touch to provide dynamic information, several quantitative empirical studies have proved that user can perceive different tactile patterns well. However, there are lack of long term in-situ studies to prove adding touch channel in remote communication is effective and emotional. If we touch the other through mechanical devices, socio-ethical issues might occur according to the body parts that are touched and who we are touching. It is important that provide users with a way to grant specific contacts a right to use touch as a communication channel because touch is very private and intimate way of expression (Heikkinen et al., 2009). Researchers in this field seem to focus highly on tactile perception and conveying / expressing different emotions through touch channel. As we noted as a one feature of remote interpersonal touch communication that touch channel is most personal and intimate among all the other sense channels.

We summarized three key design considerations for remote interpersonal touch from previous cases. First, we should consider ethical issues before we design a device/product for remote interpersonal touch communication. Second, using only tactile channel for communication might be dangerous. We understand that touch interaction is emotional; on the other hand, using only touch channel to convey a meaning/language might be very ambiguous and vague to the users. When the touch channel is accompanied with verbal spoken words, then the possibilities of enriching communication might increase. Nevertheless, if we want to convey a word with touch, we should minimize the amount of information (Heikkinen et al., 2009). Third, many researchers in HCI / Mechanical Engineering field are

exploring a variety of tactile actuators to convey emotional messages in remote. In addition, some researchers (Haans & IJsselsteijn, 2006) are saying visually induced haptic illusions (Biocca et al., 2001) are future direction of remote touch communication because additional tactile actuators might affect usability and design of the interface. Minimal approach of applying tactile actuators to convey small amount of information, and support verbal channels might be appropriate for effective remote interpersonal touch.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper represents possibilities and limitations of touch in Remote Interpersonal Interaction (RII) by 1) investigating features of current channels for RII, 2) understanding touch in the aspect of effective and emotional interaction and 3) exploring previous cases and empirical studies that applied touch in RII. From the critical review of previous researches, we found that there are certain levels of possibilities of using touch to enrich communication in remote. We suggest ways to apply touch in digital products that support RII.

1) Design a product how to enrich emotional interaction by understanding features of vocal and text channels that provides effectiveness, familiarity and naturalness of remote communication.

2) Investigate thoroughly about the social and symbolic meanings of touching / touched body part, because touching body part and touched body part is already decided as how we use the mediated digital product.

3) Consider socio-ethical issues according to the body parts that are touched and who we are touching if we touch the other through electronic products. Designers should provide users with a way to grant specific contacts a right to use touch as a communication channel because touch is very private and intimate way of expression.

4) Consider ways to combine tactile channel with other verbal channels as voice and text. Touch interaction is emotional; on the other hand, using

only touch channel to convey a meaning/language might be very ambiguous and vague to the users.

5) Minimal approach of applying tactile actuators to convey small amount of information and support verbal channels might be appropriate for effective remote interpersonal touch communication; on the other hand, overusing tactile technologies to provide realistic human-like touch feelings might decrease the applicability / feasibility on portable mobile devices that mediated interpersonal communication in the near future.

The main contribution of the study is that we attempted to explore possibilities of RII by thorough understanding of currently used communication channels and importance of touch in the aspect of human-to-human interaction. And then we set up limitations of previous cases and listed several ways to apply touch in designing digital products that supports daily remote interactions. These findings might be helpful to designers who aim to design a product that applied touch for enriching RIIs.

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